

Nuclear Chain Reaction Modelled via a Linear Hawkes Process

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803273

ABSTRACT

We propose a linear Hawkes process surrogate for nuclear chain reactions enabling event-space modelling of multiplying media. For prompt neutrons, the choice of a single-exponential excitation kernel recovers the prompt decay constant and the shapes of both the Rossi- α and Feynman- $Y(\tau)$ curves. It is found however, that the linear Hawkes surrogate enforces Poisson offspring and cannot match non-Poisson fission multiplicity, biasing the amplitudes of the second and higher factorial cumulants of gated counts (e.g. Feynman- Y_∞), while preserving time constants and modal structure. Extending the kernel with delayed channels yields a multi-exponential form whose Laplace condition for the Malthusian parameter is algebraically identical to the inhour equation, establishing modal equivalence with point kinetics. This equivalence is then showcased using a method of manufactured solutions (MMS) benchmark. Computational performance of the implemented Hawkes simulator is also discussed – several millions of neutron birth events with resolved time stamps can be simulated per second on a consumer-grade laptop. Overall, the framework allows for representation of neutron noise modelling with an established point-process methodology with future practical avenues for detector-response modelling and inference of multiplying media properties. Future work will also explore multi-region Hawkes process variants to overcome the limitations of a univariate model, which cannot capture spatial characteristics in neutron-multiplying systems.

Keywords: Branching processes, neutron noise, Hawkes process, point kinetics

1. INTRODUCTION

The view of the nuclear chain reaction as a branching process dates to the very beginning of the nuclear era, when Leo Szilard independently applied the Galton-Watson process to describe the neutron population dynamics [1]. While Galton-Watson models remain useful in some analyses [2], the standard stochastic framework in multiplying media is the Pál-Bell master-equation (generating-function) approach [3]. Methods arising from the stochastic treatment underpin reactor monitoring [4, 5], startup analysis [6, 7, 8], and the detection and characterization of nuclear material for security, safeguards, and waste management [9, 10, 11, 12]. Overall, the field remains active with novel findings continuing to appear, an example being the recent experimental observation of patchy nuclear chain reactions [13].

In practice, when the neutron-noise/branching toolkit is used for inference from experimental data, it typically relies on binned statistics and low-order moments, most notably Rossi- α or Feynman- Y [14, 15, 16]. Results can potentially depend on analyst-chosen settings such as bin width and fitting window; furthermore, extension of the underlying theoretical models by incorporating detector physics, such as dead time, typically requires the derivation of approximate corrections of the binned statistics [17, 18]. Developing the theory for multi-detector joint inference is also not a trivial task [19].

In contrast, working directly in event space could give rise to many benefits, such as the ability to handle detector physics and multiple correlated detectors at the point-process level naturally. In this paper, the approximate modelling of the nuclear chain reaction via the linear Hawkes process [20] is proposed and verified, representing a first step towards a wider framework incorporating spatial effects

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and detector response. Hawkes processes have been used for the modelling of self-exciting “chain reactions” in many real-world applications, such as infection spread, earthquake aftershocks, or stock-market transactions [20], but, to the best of author’s knowledge, their application to the modelling of physics of multiplying media appears to be absent from the open literature. As will be discussed in this paper, they do not represent the nuclear chain reaction physics perfectly. Nevertheless, linear Hawkes processes and especially those with exponential kernels are highly analytically tractable and can be simulated efficiently [20, 21]. Thus they have the potential to become a useful surrogate for chain reaction modelling.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces the linear Hawkes process and its specialisation to nuclear chain reactions, highlighting the model’s limitations and its correspondence to point kinetics. Section 3 further demonstrates this correspondence via the method of manufactured solutions and also discusses the computational performance of the Hawkes surrogate. Finally, Section 4 presents conclusions and avenues for future work.

2. CHAIN REACTION MODELLING

We begin with the following definitions adapted from [20]:

Definition 2.1 (Counting and point processes). A stochastic process $N(t)$, defined for $t \geq 0$, is a *counting process* starting at $N(0) = 0$ if $N(t)$ only takes values in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ and increases in jumps of size $+1$. The random jump times T_1, T_2, \dots form a *point process*, with $0 < T_1 < T_2 < \dots$ almost surely. The counting process can be defined in terms of the point process as:

$$N_t \equiv N(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{1}\{T_i \leq t\} = \sum_{T_i \leq t} 1. \quad (1)$$

Definition 2.2 (Conditional intensity process). The *conditional intensity process* of N_t is defined, for $t \geq 0$, by:

$$\lambda(t) = \lim_{\Delta \searrow 0} \frac{\mathbb{E}(N_{t+\Delta} - N_t \mid \mathcal{H}_t)}{\Delta}, \quad (2)$$

if this limit exists. Here \mathcal{H}_t , the *history* of N_t , is the filtration generated by $\{N_s\}_{s < t}$. Note that $\lambda(t)$ is generally a random process; if $\lambda(t)$ has no dependence on the history, then N_t is the Poisson process with rate function $\lambda(t)$.

Definition 2.3 (Linear Hawkes process). A *linear Hawkes process* is an event counting process N_t whose conditional intensity process for $t \geq 0$ is:

$$\lambda(t) = S(t) + \sum_{T_i < t} g(t - T_i), \quad (3)$$

where $S(t) \geq 0$ is the *background arrival rate* and $g : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ the *excitation function*. Equation 3 can also be written as [21]:

$$\lambda(t) = S(t) + \int_0^t g(t - u) dN(u) = S(t) + (g \star dN)(t). \quad (4)$$

In general, a Hawkes process is a Poisson-driven process: its conditional intensity function is a combination of a Poisson source term and contributions from the excitation from past events T_i , each of which generates an independent cluster according to the Poisson distribution [20]. The above linear model is a special case, in which the conditional intensity process is a simple sum of the background arrival rate and contributions from past events.

In the derivations presented in this paper, we will consider S to be independent of time, i.e. the process being stationary. This assumption can be relaxed and does not limit the generality of the presented model. We note that the self-exciting nature of the Hawkes process makes it possible for the population to “blow up”, i.e. $\mathbb{E}[N_t] = \infty$ for some finite time t [20]. At the same time, the immigration-birth view of the Hawkes process allows us to define the *branching ratio* as [20]:

$$\eta := \int_s^\infty g(t-s) dt = \int_0^\infty g(t) dt. \quad (5)$$

Then, $\eta < 1$ is a necessary and sufficient condition for the process to remain stationary and have a finite mean. Unless stated otherwise, we will consider this condition to be satisfied in the following text. For example, this allows us to write the law of large numbers for the average event rate as [20, 21]:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_t}{t} = \frac{S}{1-\eta} \quad \text{almost surely, and consequently } \mathbb{E}[\lambda(t)] = \frac{S}{1-\eta}. \quad (6)$$

As mentioned above, the direct offspring multiplicity in a Hawkes process follows a Poisson distribution [20]. This is a departure from nuclear chain reaction physics, since neutron multiplicity per fission is not Poisson; this is signified by the Diven factor D_2 , i.e. the normalized second factorial moment of the offspring distribution, being different from 1, typically $D_2 < 1$ [22, 23]. This represents the chief approximation made when the linear Hawkes process is used as a surrogate, the effects of which will be discussed below. Note that, for a Poisson offspring distribution, $D_2 = 1$.

As a final remark, the linear Hawkes process defined above as a single counting process leads to a univariate surrogate model, which cannot describe spatial effects when applied to a neutron-multiplying system. This represents a key limitation of the present model, which should be remedied in future work, e.g. by exploring multi-region Hawkes processes [20].

2.1. Prompt Neutrons Only

To motivate the use of a Hawkes model, we will start by considering only prompt neutrons. One of the simplest linear Hawkes processes is one with a single exponential kernel [20]:

$$g(t) = \eta\alpha_p \exp(-\alpha_p t). \quad (7)$$

Interpreting events (“arrivals”) as neutron births and the excitation function g as the effective reproduction kernel of fission-induced births, we identify the Hawkes branching ratio with the multiplication factor, $\eta \approx k_{\text{eff}}$, within this linear surrogate. The background arrival rate S evidently corresponds to the effective external neutron source intensity; indeed, the well-known expression for expected total neutron birth rate B in a subcritical system at steady state:

$$B = \frac{S}{1-k_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (8)$$

can be recovered from Eq. 6 by simple re-labelling. Furthermore, the covariance density of a Hawkes process with excitation function given by Eq. 7 decays exponentially with the decay constant $\alpha_{\text{decay}} = (\alpha_p - \eta\alpha_p) = (1-\eta)\alpha_p$ [21]. Thus, if we consider a chain reaction with prompt neutrons only (delayed neutron fraction $\beta_{\text{eff}} = 0$) and require this decay constant to be equal to the fundamental prompt decay constant α_{decay} [3]:

$$\alpha_{\text{decay}} = \frac{-\rho}{\Lambda} = \frac{1-k_{\text{eff}}}{\ell_p} \stackrel{!}{=} (1-\eta)\alpha_p = (1-k_{\text{eff}})\alpha_p, \quad (9)$$

we recover:

$$\alpha_p = \frac{1}{\ell_p}. \quad (10)$$

In the above, $\rho = 1 - 1/k_{\text{eff}}$ is the reactivity, ℓ_p the prompt neutron lifetime, and $\Lambda = \ell_p/k_{\text{eff}}$ the prompt neutron generation time.

With these definitions, the linear Hawkes model with excitation function (7) recovers the slope of the prompt-only Rossi- α histogram by construction. Furthermore, the definition of the Feynman- Y statistic for a gate of length τ , $Y(\tau)$ [9]:

$$Y(\tau) = \frac{\text{Var}[N_{t+\tau} - N_t]}{\mathbb{E}[N_{t+\tau} - N_t]} - 1, \quad (11)$$

can be derived for the birth counts with the help of Propositions 3.1 and 3.2 of [20] (assuming $t \rightarrow \infty$) as:

$$Y(\tau) = Y_\infty \left(1 - \frac{1 - \exp(-\alpha_{\text{decay}}\tau)}{\alpha_{\text{decay}}\tau} \right), \quad \text{where } Y_\infty = \frac{\eta(2 - \eta)}{(1 - \eta)^2}. \quad (12)$$

The term in the brackets matches the existing theory [9, 24] but the expression for Y_∞ differs from the canonical solution $Y_\infty = D_2/\rho^2$ (prompt neutrons only, perfect detection) [24] since, as mentioned above, the linear Hawkes process enforces Poisson direct offspring and therefore cannot match non-Poisson fission multiplicity, biasing the amplitudes of the second and higher factorial cumulants of gated counts. However, since Y_∞ is typically treated as a fitted parameter in practical settings [9], the Hawkes toolbox can still be useful in practice. Therefore, in the following sections, we will proceed with its extension.

2.2. With Delayed Neutrons

Having matched the prompt-only case, we now add delayed channels. First we split the branching ratio as (G is the number of precursor groups):

$$\eta = \eta_p + \sum_{i=1}^G \eta_{d,i} = (1 - \beta_{\text{eff}})k_{\text{eff}} + \sum_{i=1}^G \beta_i k_{\text{eff}}. \quad (13)$$

We assume the time from precursor creation to the subsequent fission induced by the delayed neutron comprises two independent exponential stages in sequence: (i) precursor decay and (ii) fission (births). Adding the delayed channels to the linear Hawkes model results in a multi-exponential kernel:

$$g(t) = \underbrace{\eta_p \alpha_p e^{-\alpha_p t}}_{\text{prompt}} + \sum_{i=1}^G \eta_{d,i} \underbrace{\frac{\lambda_i \alpha_p}{\lambda_i - \alpha_p} (e^{-\alpha_p t} - e^{-\lambda_i t})}_{\text{delayed group } i}. \quad (14)$$

Note that this kernel stays well-behaved for any $\lambda_i \approx \alpha_p$ with the corresponding probability density function reducing to the Erlang-2 distribution in that limit. We now find the Laplace transform of this kernel as:

$$\hat{g}(s) = \frac{\eta_p \alpha_p}{\alpha_p + s} + \sum_{i=1}^G \eta_{d,i} \frac{\lambda_i \alpha_p}{\lambda_i - \alpha_p} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_p + s} - \frac{1}{\lambda_i + s} \right) = \frac{\alpha_p}{\alpha_p + s} \left(\eta_p + \sum_{i=1}^G \eta_{d,i} \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_i + s} \right). \quad (15)$$

Substituting:

$$\hat{g}(s) = \frac{1/\ell_p}{1/\ell_p + s} \left((1 - \beta_{\text{eff}})k_{\text{eff}} + \sum_{i=1}^G \beta_i k_{\text{eff}} \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_i + s} \right) = \frac{k_{\text{eff}}}{1 + s\ell_p} \left((1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}) + \sum_{i=1}^G \beta_i \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_i + s} \right). \quad (16)$$

The condition for finding the Malthusian growth parameter $\hat{g}(s) = 1$ [25] is written as:

$$k_{\text{eff}} \left[(1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}) + \sum_{i=1}^G \beta_i \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_i + s} \right] = 1 + s\ell_p. \quad (17)$$

With the appropriate substitutions, this rearranges to the inhour equation:

$$\rho = s\Lambda + \sum_{i=1}^G \beta_i \frac{s}{s + \lambda_i}. \quad (18)$$

Thus, because $\hat{g}(s) = 1$ is algebraically identical to the inhour equation, the poles $\{s_j\}$ of $1/(1 - \hat{g}(s))$ coincide one-for-one with the point-kinetic eigenvalues $\{-\alpha_j\}$, giving time dependence $\exp(-\alpha_j t)$. As a result, the Hawkes mean intensity and the covariance density decompose into the same exponential modal set. The differences will arise only in amplitudes of higher-order quantities due to the aforementioned differences in the offspring-multiplicity model. We conclude the derivation by noting that the standard point-kinetics equations can be recovered from the mean-field Volterra equation $\mathbb{E}[\lambda(t)] = S + g(t) \star \mathbb{E}[\lambda(t)]$. The derivation of this result is too long to be detailed here and will be presented in future work. Instead, Section 3 will demonstrate it numerically.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To simulate the linear Hawkes process introduced above and including both prompt and delayed neutron channels, an exact simulator based on the superposition of independent clocks method [26] was implemented in Python 3.12 using the libraries NumPy 2.3.5 and Numba 0.62.1 with llvmlite 0.45.1 and kernels compiled with @njit(cache=True, fastmath=True) and warmed up upon initialisation. With this simulator deployed on a Dell XPS 15 9500 laptop with an Intel Core i7-10750H processor with a base clock rate of 2.60 GHz, several millions of neutron birth events can be simulated per second with the actual number depending on the parameters of the problem in question. For example, given the configuration described in [27], see Table I, the average simulated neutron birth rate was $2.7 \cdot 10^6$ events/s. This number does not depend on the degree of subcriticality of the simulated system. The reader is reminded that for each simulated neutron birth event, a time stamp is available. Given this performance, the Hawkes model could find use in real-time simulators of subcritical systems, such as the one presented in [27], allowing for a simplified representation of neutron noise. Furthermore, since the implementation used here is inherently serial and, from the point of an ensemble simulation, essentially naively parallelisable, it could also be used for inference of multiplying media characteristics, especially when detector-response modelling is incorporated into the simulation framework.

Table I. Kinetic parameters used during performance assessment and verification. Effective external neutron source intensity S was taken as 20 000 neutrons/s.

Group i	1	2	3	4	5	6	β_{eff} (pcm)	ℓ_p (μs)
β_i (pcm)	27.3	139.3	133.5	292.4	123.8	51.6	767.9	42.8
λ_i (1/s)	1.33×10^{-2}	3.27×10^{-2}	1.21×10^{-1}	3.03×10^{-1}	8.50×10^{-1}	2.85×10^0		

In lieu of a theoretical derivation, the correspondence of the reactor kinetics captured by the linear Hawkes model to the classical point kinetics will be shown next. We consider the point-kinetics equations in the form:

$$\dot{n}(t) = \frac{k_{\text{eff}}(t)(1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}) - 1}{\ell_p} n(t) + \sum_{i=1}^G \lambda_i c_i(t) + S(t), \quad (19)$$

$$\dot{c}_i(t) = \frac{k_{\text{eff}}(t)\beta_i}{\ell_p} n(t) - \lambda_i c_i(t), \quad (20)$$

where n is the neutron population and c_i the precursor population in group i . In this model, the time-dependent total neutron birth rate $B(t)$ is equal to $\dot{n}(t) + n(t)/\ell_p$, i.e. the net change of neutron population plus rate of neutron deaths. This variable can be directly compared with the results of the Hawkes

Figure 1. Total neutron birth rate in the MMS verification problem. The MMS reference and the point-kinetics solution overlap exactly. For the Hawkes ensemble solutions, the mean birth rate and its 1σ -error bars are shown; N indicates the number of trajectories per ensemble.

process simulation. As a benchmark problem, we use the method of manufactured solutions (MMS), prescribing:

$$n(t) = n_0 + A_n \sin(\omega t), \quad (21)$$

$$k_{\text{eff}}(t) = k_0 + A_k \sin(\omega t), \quad (22)$$

with $N_0 = 5.0$, $A_n = 2.5$, $k_0 = 0.9$, $A_k = 0.015$, $\omega = 2\pi/(50 \ell_p)$, and kinetics parameters as per Table I. The source term $S(t)$ in Eq. 19 is chosen so that the point-kinetics equations are satisfied exactly. Initial condition for the precursor equations is taken as zero population in all groups.

For the above problem, the numerical point-kinetics solution was found via the `integrate.solve_ivp` method of the Python library `SciPy 1.15.3` and an ensemble of Hawkes process results was obtained via the above-described simulator. Excluding the initial warm-up period of $50\ell_p$, Fig. 1 shows the comparison of the total neutron birth rate $B(t)$ as derived from the MMS ansatz, the point-kinetics solution, and the Hawkes ensemble. For the latter, the number of events was aggregated in $1.5\ell_p$ intervals. It can be seen that the point-kinetics solution overlaps with the MMS reference exactly, while the Hawkes solution converges to it as the number of trajectories in the ensemble increases. This benchmark was repeated with an artificially increased delayed-neutron fraction to clearly see the impact of delayed neutrons. The convergence of the Hawkes solution was again observed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a model of nuclear chain reactions via linear Hawkes processes was proposed. We showed that the framework is consistent with the point-kinetic model but that the linear Hawkes surrogate enforces Poisson offspring and therefore cannot reproduce non-Poisson fission multiplicity, which affects magnitudes of higher-order statistical moments while preserving time constants and modal structure. The correspondence between point kinetics and the proposed Hawkes process model was then demonstrated using a numerical MMS benchmark. Computational performance of the implemented Hawkes

simulator was also discussed – several millions of neutron births can be simulated per second on a consumer-grade laptop; thus, the Hawkes model can be used in applications such as real-time simulation of simplified representation of neutron noise and for ensemble-based inference of the characteristics of multiplying media. The latter relies on a statistical pipeline incorporating detector-response modelling, which will be implemented in future work. This will be followed by validation against experiments and benchmark datasets, especially quantifying the effects of the Poisson offspring approximation. Finally, future work will also explore multi-region Hawkes models to capture spatial effects and zonal coupling.

USE OF AI

An early brainstorming session with an AI assistant (OpenAI ChatGPT-5 Thinking) suggested exploring Hawkes processes as a surrogate for modelling neutron noise when simulating neutron detection. The potential for broader application of Hawkes processes in chain reaction modelling and their comparison to classical approaches were then investigated further in additional sessions with this AI assistant.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank Zsolt Elter for valuable discussions and comments and suggestions regarding the submitted manuscript.

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